

Jaqqot5 tutorials

Jaqqot 5: How to access and use the Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles

USE:	How to use the Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles
VERSION:	V.1.0
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INTRODUCTION

Standard experimental methods for toxicity testing in biological systems (cells, model organisms) can be overwhelmingly costly in resources as well as ethically inappropriate. Given the contemporary popularity of the nanomaterials, new in-silico approaches have been developed in order to limit the traditional experimental testing, while providing accurate results. Simeone and Costa (2019) (<https://www.doi.org/10.1039/c9en00785g>) recently developed and reported a simple, yet accurate, model to calculate the probability that nano-oxides will activate biological pathways which are causally linked to in vitro cytotoxicity. This probability is inferred from physicochemical parameters that do not need to be experimentally determined, but are available to everyone: oxidation number, ionic potential, surface reducibility, and redox reactivity. These parameters were chosen as good candidates for a Naive Bayesian classifier model, because it has been found that they determine the degree of dissolution, surface charge, surface reactivity and bulk reactivity that have been experimentally linked to toxicity. The choice of the Naive Bayesian classifier offers an important opportunity for the future, since it can be easily extended to incorporate additional sources of information as soon as they become available. The classifier predicts the most probable level of toxicity of a nanoparticle given its structural formation, based solely on the assumption that the variables used contribute independently to the probability of each toxicity level. A web application of the classifier has been implemented through the Jaqpot platform (part of the NanoCommons infrastructure) that offers all the necessary functionalities to develop the model, deploy it as a web service and share it with the scientific community as well as industry stakeholders.

Jaqpot 5 is a user-friendly web-based e-infrastructure that allows model developers to deploy their predictive models and share them through the web. The Jaqpot 5 GUI directs the model developers to further document their models in a way that can be easily understood and used by end-users with little or no experience on machine learning and statistical analysis. The GUI also allows the end-users to apply the models on their own data for validation and/or prediction purposes and the results are collected and visualised in automatically generated tables, graphs and reports. All major machine learning and statistical data-driven algorithms are supported in Jaqpot 5, by integrating popular libraries such as the Python Scikit-learn. Jaqpot 5 has been designed as a generic modelling and machine learning web platform, but particular emphasis is given on serving the needs of the chemo/bio/nano/pharma/ communities by integrating QSAR, biokinetics, dose-response and read-across models. Jaqpot 5 has been developed by the [Unit of Process Control and Informatics](#) in the School of Chemical Engineering at the National Technical University of Athens.

This document provides a tutorial on accessing and using the Naïve Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles that has been uploaded on Jaqpot5. The resource has been made available at <https://app.jaqpot.org/model/2XyMtChRiSfz6UmKirhi>.

ACCESSING AND USING THE NAÏVE BAYES MODEL FOR PREDICTION OF THE CYTOTOXICITY OF METAL OXIDE NANOPARTICLES

When the user enters Jaqpot 5 (<https://app.jaqpot.org>), either with user credentials or API key, a list of all resources (Models, Datasets) created by the user is displayed. By clicking on the “Models” tab, all available user-deployed models are displayed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. List of resources created by the user.

The user can select a specific model by placing the cursor on the model (Figure 2). When a model is selected, more information about the model are shown on the right part of the screen (model creator, creation date, description and organisations with which the model is shared).

Figure 2. Model selection.

The user can access the model by clicking on the “view» button (“eye” icon) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Opening a model.

The user has access to the Naïve Bayes model provided that membership to the NanoCommons organisation in Jaqpot exists (if not, email Professor Harry Sarimveis at hsarimv@central.ntua.gr to request membership to the organisation). To access the Naïve Bayes model, the user should click on the right arrow after the “Mine” tab on the top of the screen and select the “Shared” option in the dialogue box that appears (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Accessing models shared by other users through organisations

A new dialogue box appears listing all the organisations that the user is member of. The user should click on the NanoCommons organisation to access all available models developed under the organisation (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Selecting the NanoCommons organisation.

A list of all models shared through the NanoCommons organisation is now displayed. The user should locate the model entitled "Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles" and click on the "view" button to open the model (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Selecting the Naïve Bayes model.

By clicking the “view” button, the user is redirected to the model page, which consists of 4 tabs. The first tab available is the “Overview” tab. Here, various information about the model have been shared, including a full QSAR Model Reporting Format (QMRF) report (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The “Overview” tab of the Naive Bayes model.

In the “Features” tab the user can see information about the independent and dependent variables of the model, as well as the relevant variable levels in the Units section (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The “Features” tab of the Naïve Bayes model.

The “Predict/Validate” tab contains the main functionalities of the model (Figure 9). A user with execution rights to the model can either generate predictions for NMs with unknown end-point values or validate the model with a data set containing known end-point values (in this case toxicity level). The “Predict” option is used when the user wants to obtain predictions for new instances, where the end-point (dependent) value is unknown. Values for the independent variables can be entered manually directly on the user interface (UI). Alternatively, the user can upload a dataset through a csv template, which can be downloaded by clicking on the blue, down-pointing arrow (Figure 9). The template contains the names of all input variables, so what is left for the user is to fill in the values (one or multiple lines) and upload the dataset by clicking the red upwards-pointing arrow (Figure 9). An advantage of the csv over the UI dataset method is that the user can acquire predictions of multiple instances at once, instead of running the model once per instance, as it is needed when values are supplied directly on the UI.

Figure 9. The “Predict/Validate” tab of the Naive Bayes model – Predict Option.

The following section contains information regarding the encoding of the input and response variables. The predicted classes are: Very High Toxicity (VHT), when $\log(\text{EC50}) \leq -3$, High Toxicity (HT), when $-3 < \log(\text{EC50}) \leq -2.5$, Low Toxicity (LT), when $-2.5 < \log(\text{EC50}) \leq -2$, and finally, Very Low Toxicity (VLT), when $\log(\text{EC50}) > -2$. Four different predictor variables were considered: the oxidation number (Z), the ionic potential (IP) of the cation, the surface reducibility (SR) and the redox reactivity (RR) of the oxide. The oxidation number of the metal ion was set to category 1 for $Z \leq 2$, category 2 for $Z = 3$ and category 3 for $Z \geq 4$. The ionic potential, defined as the ratio Z/r , where r is the ionic radius measured in Angstrom, was set to category 1 for $\text{IP} \leq 3$, category 2 for $3 < \text{IP} \leq 5$ and category 3 for $\text{IP} > 5$. Surface reducibility was used to describe the type of defects that form at the surface of nano-oxides. For a given oxide of known composition, category 1 encodes “reducible”, category 2 encodes “non reducible” and category 3 encodes “oxidizable”. To decide if a nanoparticle was “active” or “non active”, the reduction potential of the oxide at $\text{pH} = 7$ was calculated and compared with the redox potential of the cell: nanoparticles with a redox potential $< -0.8 \text{ V}$ (versus SHE, that is, the standard hydrogen reduction potential) were assigned the value “non active” (category 1); while nanoparticles with a reduction potential $> -0.8 \text{ V/SHE}$ at $\text{pH} = 7$, were considered “active” (category 2). Note: The redox potential at $\text{pH}=7$ can be easily calculated from the values of the standard redox potentials through the Nernst equation.

With the above information the user can formulate an instance/instances for several metal oxide nanoparticles and get an estimation of their cytotoxicity, either by entering an instance of input variables directly on the UI or by uploading a csv containing instance(s) for prediction, as mentioned before. Figure 10 presents the case where the completion of an instance of input variables takes place directly on the UI, where after filling in all values, the “start procedure” button is activated. By clicking on this button, the prediction procedure starts. Figure 11 presents an example of a csv dataset.

Figure 10. Example of completing the prediction tab on the UI. Here we are requesting a prediction from the Naïve Bayes model for a nanomaterial with ionic potential $IP \leq 3$, oxidation number $Z \leq 2$, “active” redox reactivity and “reducible” surface reducibility.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Oxidation Number Z	Redox Reactivity RR	Surface Reducibility SR	Ionic Potential IP				
2	1	1	1	2				
3	3	1	2	1				
4	2	2	2	2				
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								

Figure 11. Example of a csv dataset. The numbers come from the variable level encoding, which can be found in the “Features” tab.

After clicking on the red arrow and selecting a dataset to upload, a window pops up and the user is prompted to provide a dataset id, in which case the “None” option should be selected and then the continue button should be pressed (Figure 12). Following that, a preview of the dataset is displayed and a “start procedure” button is activated, as in the previous case of filling in the values directly on the UI (Figure 13). If the uploaded dataset is not the desired one, the user can press the “erase dataset” button to enable the upload of another dataset (Figure 13).

Figure 12. Dataset id selection window. The user should select None and click to continue.

Figure 13. Dataset preview.

Once the prediction task starts, the user is informed about its progress. When the task is completed, a “View prediction” button appears on the bottom of the screen (blue “double-check” icon). By clicking on the button, the user can view the results of the prediction task (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Prediction procedure progress.

Both the dependent and independent variables are appended on a matrix and presented in a tabular format (Figure 15). The dataset can be downloaded by clicking on the “Download” button. Each page can hold up to 30 rows, so if more than 30 instances were provided, the user can turn prediction pages by clicking on the arrows on the bottom right end of the page. Moreover, the user can switch to viewing only the dependent variable, in this case the toxicity class, by clicking on the “View predicted value only” button. To return to viewing all variables, the user should click on the “View all” button (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Presentation of the results of the prediction tab (all variables mode).

Figure 16. Presentation of the results of the prediction tab (only dependent variable mode).

Returning back to the “Choose method” section on the “Predict/Validate” tab, the user can switch from the “Predict” to the “Validate” option in order to test the model. Here the only available option is to upload a dataset in a csv format (Figure 17). The dataset upload procedure is exactly the same (select “None” again on the dataset id window), with the only difference being that now the dataset contains instances with both the 4 independent variables and the toxicity class, which is considered to be known beforehand. An example of a validation dataset is presented in Figure 18.

Figure 17. The “Predict/Validate” tab of the Naïve Bayes model – Validate Option.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Surface Reducibility SR	Oxidation Number Z	Ionic Potential IP	Redox Reactivity RR	Class of toxicity			
2	1	1	3		1 VHT			
3	1	1	2		1 VHT			
4	2	3	2		1 VHT			
5	3	3	2		1 HT			
6	2	2	3		2 HT			
7								
8								
9								
10								

Figure 18. Example of a validation dataset.

Now, the “Start procedure” button is activated after the selection of the validation method. Since the predicted variable is categorical, the user should choose the “Validation for classification” button (“three dots” icon) and then click on the “Start procedure” button (Figure 19).

MODEL
 Title: Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles
 Owner: Haralampos Sarimveis
 Description:
 Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles using fundamental physical-chemical parameters

Upload dataset with the required features and values

Dataset formed

Id	Surface Reducibility SR	Oxidation Number Z	Redox Reactivity RR	Ionic Potential IP	Class of toxicity
8	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	0

Choose validation method

Click on the “Validation for classification” button

Start procedure Erase dataset

Figure 19. Preview of the validation dataset and initiation of the validation procedure.

After initiating the validation procedure, a detailed report of the ongoing validation task is displayed on the screen, just like the one appearing in the prediction task (Figure 14). After clicking on the “View report” button (blue “double check” icon), a report presenting the validation statistics of the model is displayed (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Validation report of the model.

Finally, in the “Discussion” tab any user can leave a comment or reply to a previous comment (Figure 21):

Figure 21. The “Discussion” tab.

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